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Development and Modernization

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Abstract: *The study proposes and analyzes the importance of such effects and emerging factors that determine new directions in this area. In accordance with the purpose of the study, the following tasks were identified: ethical, socio-cultural aspects of individual thinking in human development and activities to help others, modernization, modernization, transformation, the role and solution of new behavior in management.*

Key words: *behavior, modernization, socio-cultural values, development, transformation.*

Introduction

The purpose of the article is to study a new model of behavior in Azerbaijan, ethical aspects of individual thinking in management: essence, principles and formation. Along with the modernization aspects of the problem, its mutual analysis with many issues requiring the development of human thinking, actualizes the solution of various problems. In this regard, the analysis and study of the subjective aspects of human activity in philosophy can significantly affect the development of management.

Research methods and methodology. The research was carried out on the basis of comparative, induction, deductive, systemic, general logic, methods.

The degree of study of the problem Durkheim Emile, A. V. Mitrofanova, M. Beber, H.Q. İbrahimov, Ş. M. Mamedov and M. Afandiev others studied this topic. Scientific innovation. The article examines the issues of modernization of individual thinking in the context of new transformations taking place in our country in modern times in harmony with sociocultural and ethical values.

Results. The article examines the ongoing modernization, transformations, new behavior, features of individual thinking in our country and concludes that important issues in management, as well as important aspects of sociocultural life stereotypes in this process.

Main Part

1. Intelligent management problem

One of them is to prevent the flow of people from rural areas to urban areas: "That is, to create conditions for people in rural areas so that they have access to all the services they can get in the city." The second goal of the "Smart Village" project is to create an opportunity for people to earn money in the village (1).

The third issue is that, like every citizen of the country, rural residents should have access to public services.

To solve all these problems, innovative rural projects are used around the world. « There are 3 main components. The first is smart infrastructure and services, the second is smart economy and business, and the third is smart public administration.

The idea of "smart villages" is not new in the world and exists in several countries. For example, there is a "Smart Village" project in Turkey with the support of "Vodafone". Kazakhstan has the "Village Kazakhstan" project, Rwanda has the "Smart Village" project, and Ukraine has the "Autonomous Smart Village" project.

What happens in "smart villages"?

In "Smart Villages", high-speed Internet, e-health system - which reports the answer of 36 types of analysis in 10 minutes - electronic services are provided to citizens, there is an electronic classroom, biometric passports are issued. In "Smart Villages" there are also ATM pharmacies that sell medicines (3).

In Germany, the "Smart Village" project is implemented in 4 locations, the largest of which is in the city of Eisenberg. Smart trade and logistics, smart energy methods are used here (2).

In Finland and Lapland, e-education, e-medicine, alternative energy, e-commerce and transport have developed: "For example, in Lapland, such an application has been created for mobile phones that a person who wants to go to the city enters this program and sees who will go to the city tomorrow and how many free spaces are there in the car? Azerbaijan prevents threats in the region with smart projects

I wonder if this visit will bring peace to this country or increase the risks of conflict. An environment of stability has been created in the South Caucasus for 4 years since the collapse of the USSR. Azerbaijan has removed the military junta regime from Garabagh, social construction works have been started in the region. It was important for Y. Stoltenberg to pay attention to such important factors. In our opinion, NATO should increase its efforts to strengthen peace today and should clearly state what and to whom it directs its military blocking power. The collision of civilizations is not a meteorite event. It will happen sooner or later. Instead, political conflicts, which are calculated to lead many nations to face local wars before this conflict, are undesirable.

Azerbaijan has entered a new stage in the development of its complex transition process. This stage is characterized by the transformation of new knowledge and the possibilities of new postmodern application of management forms and methods. The establishment of statehood, year-by-year strengthening of sovereignty, the settlement of the Armenian-Azerbaijani conflict with a just victory, the liberation of our lands from occupation, and principled calls for the dialogue of cultures are important historical events. The 18th Summit of the heads of state and government of the Non-Aligned Movement in Baku ensures that Azerbaijan will host this great movement until 2022. When we look at

the sequence of socio-economic and cultural policy, we clearly see that the processes coincide with the provisions put forward by the head of the country in the election platform. Smart Villages are a relatively new concept in EU policy making. The emerging concept of Smart Villages refers to rural areas and communities that build on existing strengths and assets as well as develop new capabilities. Smart Villages improve traditional and new networks and services for the benefit of residents and businesses through better use of digital, telecommunications technologies, innovation and knowledge. Digital technologies and innovations promote quality of life, higher living standards, public services for citizens, better use of resources, and less negative impact on the environment.

A Smart Village typically focuses on e-literacy skills, e-health and the following other key services: innovative solutions for environmental problems, circular economy application to agricultural waste, promotion of local products supported by technology and ICT, implementation of smart specialized agri-food projects and getting full benefits from it, tourism and cultural activities, etc.

The goals of creating a smart village are:

One of them is to prevent the flow of people from rural areas to urban areas: "That is, to create conditions for people in rural areas so that they have access to all the services they can get in the city." The second goal of the "Smart Village" project is to create an opportunity for people to earn money in the village (1).

One of the most important principles of legitimacy in a democracy is transformation through reforms and implementation of election platform promises [8.p. 52]. The principles of reforms in our country were carried out adequately to the wishes of the people and the challenges of the world, raising Azerbaijan to the ranks of the most influential countries in the world and aimed at strengthening the interests of every Azerbaijani in the modern turbulent world. Speeches of the head of the country at the Valday meeting, principledness and great erudition in the meeting with the head of Armenia;

➤ The bravery of the Commander-in-Chief in liberating our territories from occupation

1.2 Forming a modern political system on a strong economic foundation

Today, Azerbaijan is a dynamically developing, modern country that meets its own needs. Our policy is very open and clear. Forming a modern political system on a strong economic foundation, strengthening the foundations of statehood, and strengthening the ideology of Azerbaijaniism are priority issues for us... We have restored and preserved our independence. Today we are strengthening independence. Independence is the greatest wealth, the greatest blessing, the greatest value for us". The idea that independence is a supreme value, being a high political and cultural thought, has become an important principle in the transformation of the elite today. This idea also opens the way for a new era by combining the philosophy of modern management. (in fact, I would say that old states) have their own management philosophies. They have formed and applied their management philosophies. The formation of the philosophy of modern young states can have more objective difficulties.

Conclusion

So, while concluding the article, we want to highlight our scientific conclusion. So that Azerbaijan has completed the transition process on its socio-economic ground, and the transition process on the ideological ground is constantly ongoing. Public consciousness has a developed level. Social consciousness is a manifestation of the material and moral relations formed in the process of people's relation to each other and to nature [4.p.17]. This manifestation is also important as a high socio-cultural factor. Staged intercultural dialogue-forums with the participation of most of the countries of

the world were born out of this necessity. Therefore, in order to fill the ideological gap, it is not the role of the world being a young or old state, but the fact that the principles and ideas are humane and mastered by the masses.

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